

A New Gravimetric Method for the Estimation of Nickel, Cobalt and Cadmium.

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It has already been shown by one of us that hydrazine gives insoluble compounds with thiocyanates of bivalent metals, such as Ni, Co, Cd, Mn and Zn having the constitution, $[M^{11}(N_2H_4)_2](SCN)_2$ (Ray and Sarkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 822). In the present paper, the sensitiveness of the above reactions has been studied and it has been found to furnish a most rapid and accurate general method for the quantitative estimation of cobalt, cadmium, and nickel, if present alone. A further investigation has been made with other divalent metals of the magnesium family *vis.*, Mg, Fe¹¹, Cr¹¹, V¹¹.

The compounds, Ni(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄, Co(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄, Cd(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄; Zn(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄ are all stable compounds and have similar chemical and physical properties. These are all sparingly soluble in water, the solubility however increasing in the order Ni, Co, Cd and Zn.

The general procedure for quantitative estimation consists in precipitating cobalt, cadmium, and nickel from the solutions of their salts, when free from other metals or from one another, as M¹¹(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄. The precipitate is transferred to a silica or asbestos Gooch, and washed with a dilute solution of the precipitants. Finally it is washed with absolute alcohol and dried in a steam-oven. The precipitate is weighed as M¹¹(SCN)₂·2N₂H₄.

Estimation of Cobalt.

When a dilute neutral solution of cobalt salt is treated with ammonium thiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate, a flesh coloured silky crystalline precipitate of cobalt thiocyanate-hydrazine is formed.

The precipitate is very slightly soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol and other common organic solvents.

Limit of Sensitiveness.—The reaction is sensitive enough to detect the presence of 10^{-3} g. of cobalt per c.c. After a systematic investigation, the following procedure for the complete precipitation of cobalt was established.

Procedure.—Dilute the neutral or slightly acid solution of the sulphate, chloride or nitrate, so that not more than 0.15 g. of cobalt is present in 200 c.c.; treat with 10 to 15 times the theoretical amount of ammonium thiocyanate, heat to about 70° , stirring well. Add drop by drop, a very dilute aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate adding two to three drops in excess and allow to settle. The precipitate is filtered through an asbestos or silica Gooch.

First Washing.—As the compound, $\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ is slightly soluble in water but quite insoluble in alcohol, it has to be washed free from sulphate, nitrate or chloride with the following wash-liquor.

Wash-liquor.—15 c.c. rectified spirit, 75 c.c. water, 1.5 g. ammonium thiocyanate, and 0.025 g. hydrazine hydrate.

Second Washing.—The precipitate is then washed with absolute alcohol and freed from thiocyanate, hydrazine and traces of water. The alcohol is removed as far as possible by sucking a current of air through it; finally it is dried, in the steam-oven and weighed as $\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ (Co = 24.7%).

When the solution contains more than 0.15 g. of cobalt per 200 c.c. oxidation takes place (in presence of an excess of ammonium sulphate, nitrate or chloride) in alkaline solution, hence the precipitation of cobalt is not complete. If, however, the precipitation be carried out in an atmosphere of hydrogen with a further increment of usual volume, quite satisfactory results are obtained. A few precautions for the successful operation of the method are as follows:

(1) The solution containing cobalt must not be highly acidic, as it involves an unnecessary expenditure of hydrazine hydrate, at the same time the precipitate assumes a brownish tint probably due to the formation of cobaltic oxide.

(2) Hydrazine hydrate must not be added in more than five times the theoretical quantity. Otherwise hydrogen sulphide which is formed to some extent causes the formation of cobalt sulphide.

(3) The filtration should be done at 35° . When filtered hot, the result is a little low.

(4) During filtration a strong current of air should not be sucked in through the precipitate until it is finally washed with

alcohol. If exposed to air for a long time in presence of the precipitants, black cobalt sulphide is sometimes formed.

(5) The precipitate when placed in the oven for drying should be free from all traces of water. Hot water decomposes the compound into a bluish hydroxide.

A few of the preliminary data which led to the establishment of the conditions are as follows:—

(a) *Influence of temperature.*

Temperature.	Time required to settle.	Cobalt actually present.	Cobalt found.	Error.
Precipitation carried at room temperature	About one hour.	0·1235g.	0·1239g.	—·0002
Pptn. carried at room temp. 30°, cooled to 0° and filtered.	The ppt. settled as the temp. began to fall.	0·1235	0·1232	—·0003
Pptn. carried at a temp. above 70° and digested on the water-bath (98-99°) for 25 minutes, cooled to 30°, filtered.	Precipitate settled in 20 mins. in comparatively big grains.	0·1235	0·1230	—·0005
Pptn. carried at about 65° and cooled to 35°.	During the cooling the ppt. settled very well in less than half an hour.	0·1235	0·1234	—·0001
Pptn. carried in warm soln. at about 65° and allowed to cool and settle overnight.		0·1235	0·1232	—·0003

(b) *Influence of increasing concentration of ammonium thiocyanate.*

Ammon. thiocyanate used.	Cobalt actually present.	Cobalt found.	Error.
4 times the theoretical amount.	0·1235 g.	0·1234 g. (The ppt. was not so well crystalline).	—0·0001
10 times the ..	0·1235	0·1233	—0·0002
15 times the ..	0·1235	0·1234	—0·0001

(c) *Influence of excess of hydrazine.*

Hydrazine hydrate used.	Cobalt actually present.	Cobalt found.	Error.
10 times the theoretical amount.	0·1235 g.	0·1225 g.	—0·0009

A solution of extra pure cobalt nitrate free from nickel, iron and other heavy metals, sulphates, chlorides, etc., was used. The actual quantity of cobalt present, was determined by duplicate electrolytic estimations and in some cases by the sulphate method. Calibrated burettes and weights were used.

TABLE I.

Actual amount of cobalt present.	Amount of cobalt found.	Error.
0·1235 g.	0·1232 g.	-·0003
0·1235	0·1233	-·0002
0·1235	0·1232	-·0003
0·1235	0·1234	-·0001
0·1074	0·1074	-·0000
0·1074	0·1074	"
0·0822	0·0819	-·0003
0·0658	0·0656	-·0002
0·0411	0·0410	-·0001
0·0165	0·0166	+·0001

With quantities of cobalt greater than 0·15 g. the results obtained were low but the difficulty was overcome as would be evident from the following table:—

TABLE II.

(a) *With quantities more than 0·15 g. per 200 c.c.*

Amount of cobalt present.	Cobalt found.	Error.
0·1911 g.	0·1794 g.	-·0017
0·2881	0·2853	-·0028

(b) *The volume was increased to 800 c.c.*

0·2881 g.	0·2865 g.	-·0016
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(c) *In an atmosphere of hydrogen, volume as in (a).*

0·3222 g.	0·3210 g.	-·0012
0·2148	0·2141	-·0007

(d) *In an atmosphere of hydrogen and with increased volume.*

0·2148 g.	0·2146 g.	-·0002
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Presence of the salts of alkalis and alkaline earth metals or magnesium does not interfere with the estimation, if the precipitations be made in an atmosphere of hydrogen with dilute solutions.

Estimation of Cadmium.

A white crystalline compound, $Cd(SCN)_2 \cdot 2N_2H_4$ is obtained on adding ammonium thiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate to a cadmium solution.

Limit of Sensitiveness.—The reaction is sensitive enough to detect the presence of 1.8×10^{-3} g. of cadmium per c.c.

The compound is more soluble in water than that of cobalt. The cadmium compound is slightly dissolved even in presence of the precipitating reagents. The precipitation of cadmium is only complete either at a very low temperature or in an alcoholic medium of definite concentration at ordinary temperature. The cadmium compound is insoluble in other common organic solvents. After a systematic study, the following procedure has been adopted for a quantitative estimation.

Procedure.—Dilute the neutral or slightly acid solution, so that not more than 0.1 g. of cadmium is present in 100 c.c.; treat with 10 to 15 times the theoretical quantity of ammonium thiocyanate. Stir and carefully add drop by drop very dilute aqueous hydrazine hydrate until the precipitation begins, add two or three drops more and allow it to settle for a minute or two. Then add 50 c.c. of 30 per cent. alcohol and cool the solution below 12°. By this time the precipitate has completely settled. A silica or asbestos Gooch is used for filtration and the precipitate is washed with the following liquor:—

100 C.c. of 25 per cent. alcohol solution + 1.5 g. of NH_4SCN + 0.025 g. of hydrazine hydrate. It is finally washed with absolute alcohol and dried at a temperature below 80°. For successful operations similar precautions should be taken as in the case of cobalt.

A few of the preliminary data which led to the correct procedure are as follows:

TABLE II.

Conditions.	Cadmium actually present.	Cadmium found.	Error.
At the room temp. in aqueous soln. washed with the liquor as in the case of cobalt (aqueous).	0.1089 g.	0.1050 g.	-0.0039
After pptn. the soln. cooled below 5° and washed with alcoholic liquor.	0.1089	0.1080	-0.0009
Pptn. carried in 15% alcoholic soln.	0.1089	0.1081	-0.0008
Pptn. carried in 20 per cent. alcoholic soln.	0.1089	0.1090	+0.0001

An "extra pure" variety of Merck's cadmium sulphate guaranteed to be free from zinc, iron, etc., was used. The cadmium in solution was estimated in duplicate by the pyrophosphate method. The following estimations were made by the new method:—

TABLE IV.

Amount of cadmium actually present.	Amount of cadmium found by the new method.	Error.
0.2728 g.	0.2723 g.	0
0.2178	0.2182	+0.0004
0.1743	0.1747	"
0.1089	0.1092	+0.0003
"	0.1091	+0.0002
"	0.1090	+0.0001
0.1088	0.1035	-0.0003
0.0762	0.0761	-0.0001
0.0544	0.0542	-0.0002
0.0272	0.0271	-0.0001
0.0109	0.0110	+0.0001

Estimation of Nickel.

The bluish-violet, very finely divided precipitate of $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$, $2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ is practically insoluble in water and is the most stable compound of the series.

Limit of Sensitiveness.— 0.8×10^{-5} G. of nickel per c. c. can be detected.

The precipitate being very fine care must be taken during filtration and washing. Nickel is quantitatively precipitated, with any concentration of ammonium thiocyanate and hydrazine but the precipitate takes time to settle. The following procedure has been found to be the best:—

Procedure.—Dilute the neutral or slightly acid solution of nickel chloride so that 0.1 g. of Ni is present in 150 c. c. of solution; add 2 g. of NH_4SCN , heat to boiling, stir well and precipitate with 5 to 10 times the theoretical quantity of hydrazine hydrate. Allow the precipitate to settle for half an hour, when it is ready for filtration (the precipitate being slimy does not settle well). Filtration becomes

more easy if the precipitate be allowed to stand overnight. An asbestos or silica Gooch No. 4 is used. The precipitate is washed with the same wash-liquor as used in the case of cobalt; finally washed with absolute alcohol and dried in a steam-oven. Weighed as the original compound $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$. An "extra pure" sample of nickel chloride guaranteed to be free from cobalt, iron and other heavy metals was used. The actual quantity of nickel was found by duplicate estimation as nickel dimethyl glyoxime.

Amount of nickel actually present.	Amount of nickel found out by the new method.	Error
0.2255 g.	0.2255 g.	Nil
0.1804	0.1804	"
0.1353	0.1352	-0.0001
0.1902	0.0907	-0.0005
0.0451	0.0451	Nil
0.0890	0.0886	-0.0004
0.0390	0.0390	Nil

Some more new compounds of the series $\text{R}''(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ have been prepared.

Compound of Ferrous Thiocyanate and Hydrazine.

A solution of ferrous sulphate was mixed with a concentrated solution of ammonium thiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate added drop by drop. A white crystalline precipitate was obtained which gradually turned yellowish-red on exposure to air. When the compound is formed in alcoholic solution and washed with alcohol, the compound is fairly stable. When dissolved in water a green precipitate of ferrous hydroxide is obtained. Dilute ammonia gives green $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$. The dry substance decomposes to black oxide of iron (FeO) at about 90° . (Found: Fe, 23.7; S, 26.8; N_2H_4 , 27.61. $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ requires Fe, 23.7; S, 27.1; N_2H_4 , 27.12 per cent.).

Compound of Magnesium Thiocyanate with Hydrazine.

Magnesium in addition to its relationship to calcium and other two alkaline earths shows several points of resemblance to nickel, cobalt, zinc, iron (bivalent), etc., in forming a few analogous bivalent salts, e.g., isomorphous sulphates like $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; NiSO_4 ,

$7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; etc., and isomorphous double sulphate like $\text{K}_2\text{Mg}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{K}_2\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{K}_2\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ etc., and insoluble double phosphates like $\text{Mg}(\text{NH}_4)\text{PO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_4)\text{PO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Mn}(\text{NH}_4)\text{PO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The bivalent oxides of magnesium and iron are constantly associated together in nature as isomorphous mixture of silicates in minerals such as olivine $(\text{MgFe})_2\text{SiO}_4$ and hornblende $(\text{MgFe})\text{SiO}_3$. The behaviour of magnesium suggested that a compound analogous to $\text{R}''(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ etc., might be obtained, by the action of hydrazine hydrate on magnesium thiocyanate. Magnesium acetate and ammonium thiocyanate were dissolved in absolute alcohol, warmed a little, an absolute alcoholic solution of hydrazine hydrate was added, and after vigorous stirring a precipitate appeared. Drained and washed with absolute alcohol, and dried, a white crystalline substance was obtained. Contrary to the previous hydrazine thiocyanate compound, it is highly soluble in water. In the dry state it is fairly stable; when heated above 60° decomposes into the oxide. (Found: Mg, 10.9 ; S, 30.08 ; N_2H_4 , 30.4. $\text{Mg}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ requires Mg, 11.26 ; S, 30.05 ; N_2H_4 , 30.05 per cent.).

All the salts of the series $\text{R}''(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ described appear under the polarisation microscope double refracting and exhibit oblique extinction. Their suitability for microchemical detection specially that of zinc will be communicated shortly.

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